

Problems of Compensation for Damage to the Life and Health of a Citizen

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Abstract: This article analyzes issues such as the civil legal bases of damage to the life and health of a citizen, the concept and types of such damage. Also, problems of compensation for damage caused to the life and health of the citizen were scientifically analyzed and suggestions and recommendations were given.

Keywords: delict, damage, victim, wrongful act, responsibility, damager, compensation for damage, causation, guilt.

One of the inalienable human rights that belongs to everyone from the moment of birth is the right to life, which is enshrined in international documents, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, the Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, as well as other normative documents. The right to life is enshrined in the constitutions of most countries of the world, as well as in the Constitution of Uzbekistan. This right is crucial in the sense that many constitutional rights, such as the right to health and the right to a safe environment, have the main purpose of contributing to the realization of the right to life.

Declaring human life and health, human rights and freedoms as the highest value in the Basic Law imposes on the state obligations to ensure a decent standard of living of citizens, their personal freedom and inviolability. It is impossible to achieve this goal without developing an appropriate legal mechanism to prevent harm and protect the rights and interests of citizens at the constitutional and branch level.

It is known that even in Roman law there were obligations arising from delicts, including what was called personal pain, suffering, as one of the types of damage to health. Nevertheless, problems related to compensation for damage to the life or health of a citizen are undoubtedly unique to society at the beginning of the 21st century.

In the situation where there are many gaps in the legislation of Uzbekistan, frequent inconsistencies between theory and practice, the conditions for the full functioning of universal relations deserve special attention. In this regard, non-contractual obligations arising not on the basis of a concluded contract, but on other grounds provided by law, have recently become especially important in modern civil society. According to Article 8 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, one of such legal facts is harming another person by one person. The regulation of relations on compensation for damage to intangible goods such as life and health of a citizen is not only theoretical, but also of practical importance, because it affects his life values, in which other values of the material or spiritual world completely or more lose their importance.

Harm to the life or health of citizens is one of the common bases of obligations arising from harm. At different times, such relations were vaguely regulated. Responsibility for damage caused by harm to the

health or death of a citizen has not always met the requirements of conscience, discretion and justice. At the same time, the judicial practice of recent years indicates a constant increase in the number of civil cases related to the consideration of non-contractual damages. The analysis of judicial practice showed that in the context of the development of compulsory health insurance and the strengthening of the consumer rights movement, the number of cases of patients turning to judicial bodies and regional societies for the protection of consumer rights with claims for compensation for damages caused by improper medical care is increasing sharply.

In addition, claims for compensation for damage to life or health as a result of a terrorist act are becoming increasingly important and relevant. Uzbekistan is a party to many international treaties on the fight against terrorism, for example, the Convention on Combating the Financing of Terrorism, the Convention on Combating Nuclear Terrorism. Unfortunately, we must admit that the directions of development of the state and society defined in the documents do not always correspond to the real reality, which is confirmed by many trials of victims of terrorist attacks. Usually, the state has assumed the task of compensating the victims of terrorism, but the law "On the fight against terrorism" does not contain clear legal structures, in particular, the norms regulating the compensation of damage to the life or health of a citizen are applied at the discretion of existing judges. On the same issues, the courts make completely opposite decisions, assuming the same rule of law, and the amount of compensation often does not allow the victim to recover at least partially his previous situation.

In this regard, the legislator is actively implementing measures to improve the legal mechanism that increases responsibility for the life and health of citizens. The activity of the state in improving the legal mechanism is clearly expressed in the Constitution of Uzbekistan, first of all, in strengthening the right to intangible benefits and their protection; secondly, "obligations arising from damage" in Chapter 57 of the FC, as well as in other laws and other regulatory legal documents; thirdly, the established norms contain a number of provisions on compensation for damage caused to the life or health of a citizen.

The concept of damage is one of the main concepts of civil and delict law. Delict is an act of causing harm, and the consequence of that act is harm. Damage to the life and health of citizens occupies one of the important places in the obligation to compensate for damage, to which the provisions of paragraph 2 of Chapter 57 of the FC are applied, including the general rules of the obligation to compensate for damage of the FC. However, in legal documents and scientific legal literature, there is no single point of view on what should be understood by damage to the life and health of a citizen.

In civil law, the term "damage" is often used, but the legislature does not provide a legal definition of the concept of damage. Scientific literature suggests that "damage to human health is understood as a violation of the anatomical integrity and physiological functions of human organs and tissues under the influence of physical, chemical, biological and mental factors." This opinion represents harm to health from the point of view of criminal law. Although civil legislation, including FC, is related to the norms containing the basic provisions on compensation for damage to life and health, no clear explanations have been given in this regard. In this regard, difficulties arise due to the correctness of the practical application of norms and the lack of clear formulas in understanding what should be understood as damage to life and health from the point of view of civil law.

If damage is considered in the most general form, according to the words of L.V. Tikhomirov, "damage in civil law means any reduction and negative change of personal or property benefits" ¹. In civil law, not the diminution of personal or property benefits, but only the negative consequences resulting from such a diminution for the victim have legal significance. These adverse effects may be property or non-property in nature, that is, they may have a monetary value or may not have an equivalent value. In this regard, damage is divided into property and non-property, that is, moral damage.

Some authors consider this concept more broadly and define damage as a set of unpleasant (negative)

¹ Vozmeshchenie vreda, prichinennogo jizni ili zdorovyu / L.V. Tikhomirova, M.Yu. Tikhomirov. - M.: Izd-vo Tikhomirova M.Yu., 2011. - 12 c.

consequences that occur in connection with the offense². However, these consequences arise only as a result of the violation, and from the point of view of civil law, the damage that gives rise to the obligation to compensate and compensate is of interest.

In the civil-legal literature, there are different opinions about what should be understood as damage to life and health. According to O. O. Sherstneva, "damage to a citizen's health is expressed as an injury, occupational disease or other damage to his health³." T.E. Abova and A.Yu. According to Kabalkin, "damage to the life and health of a citizen is expressed in the death of a person or injury or damage to him⁴." In all cases, such damages cannot be compensated in kind or in cash. The victim, as a rule, has property losses, because due to injuries, injuries, he is temporarily or permanently deprived of the opportunity to receive wages or other income, and instead has to absorb treatment, rehabilitation, etc.

Thus, based on the above opinions of the authors, it is possible to notice the similarity of their points of view, each of these authors associates injury with damage to life and health. However, the definition given by O. O. Sherstneva mentions another harm to health, which may include the injuries reported by T. E. Abova and A. Yu. Kabalkin. Based on the comparison of these points, we can say that a more successful definition of damage to life and health was expressed by T. E. Abova and A. Yu. Kabalkin, because they use a wider range of social relations in their definitions, and O. O. Sherstneva in his definition shows the existence of an occupational disease, limited to labor relations.

In this regard, T.I. A different approach is proposed by Lysenko, and he writes that "damage to life and health means the loss of a person's condition, loss of proper and normal functioning of his body, including disturbances in the physical, mental, social and other conditions of a person⁵." V.A. Vorobyov analyzes damage from the point of view of compensation for the deterioration of human life and health and understands damage as "death caused by violence or damage caused to a person's health under the influence of an external influence against his will⁶."

Thus, based on the above, summarizing the opinions of civilians and legal norms, to understand the harm caused to the life and health of citizens as unfavorable property and non-property consequences in the form of injury or death of a citizen, expressed in life or health and injury caused by illegal aggression for the injured citizen it can be concluded that it is necessary⁷. From a civil-legal point of view, life and health are important, not damage to benefits protected by law, only any property and non-property consequences that are unfavorable to the aggrieved citizen for the reduction of these benefits and encroachment on him are important. In this regard, it is necessary to amend the title of Chapter 57 of the FC and a number of articles using incorrect words in this chapter, which will contribute to the clear and correct application of the law.

Damage to life and health has traditionally been defined by the legislator as a separate delict, because it refers to encroachment on specific benefits of intangible (ideal) nature, causing intangible damage, which complicates the creation of an acceptable compensation mechanism for the damage caused. Life and health are the highest values, damage to life or health that does not have a monetary value is not compensated in principle. As noted in one of the reviews of the practice of the Supreme Court, the damage to the health of citizens really means irreparable and incalculable damage, which is the basis for forcing

² Slesarev V.L. Object i result grajdanskogo pravonarusheniya. - Tomsk: Izd-vo Tom. flour, 1980. - S. 40–43.

³ Course of civil law. T. 2.: Uchebnik v 2-x tomakh / Pod ed. O.O. Sherstnevoy. - M.: Omega, 2008. - 317 p.

⁴ Abova T.E. Commentary on the Civil Code of the Russian Federation. V 2 t. T.1. Chasti 1, 2 GK RF / pod ed. T.E. Abovoy, A.Yu. Kabalkina. - M.: Yurayt, 2010. - 718 p.

⁵ Lysenko T.I. Civil-law institute vozmeshcheniya vnedogovernogo vreda, prichinennogo jizni ili zdorovyu grajdanina: avtoref. dis. ... candy. walk science - Kazan, 2006. - 8 p.

⁶ Vorobev V.A. Pravo cheloveka na kompensatsiyu vreda, prichinennogo jizni i zdorovyu, po zakonodatelstvu RF (civil-law aspect): avtoref. dis. ... candy. walk science - M.: 2008. - 18 p.

⁷ Golovyryna M.A. Ponyatie vreda, prichinennogo zhizni i zdorovyu grajdan // <http://conf.omua.ru/content/ponyatie-vreda-prichinennogo-zhizni-i-zdorovyu-grazhdan>

the state to act for full compensation.

Damage to these benefits can be the basis for certain property losses, which are compensated in accordance with the provisions of paragraph 2 of Chapter 57 of the FC. However, law enforcement officials, when considering cases of this category, should not forget the specific nature of the harm caused to life or health, it is very important to observe the principles of justice in compensation. Unfair court decisions not only increase mental suffering, but can also cause physical pain and loss.

Damage to health, first of all, consists of income (income) lost by the victim and additional costs incurred due to damage to health (Part 1 of Article 1006 of the Criminal Code).

Salary (income) refers to the funds received or may be received by the victim under labor and civil legal contracts, as well as from entrepreneurship and other activities (for example, authorship, creativity) before the injury or other damage to health.

Compensation depends not only on the wages that were not actually received for the work, but also on the income that the victim could have received in practice if the health of the victim had not been harmed⁸.

Since the compensation is aimed at protecting the property interests of the victims, the law does not allow to reduce its amount due to the pension (including disability), benefits and other similar payments awarded to the victim both before and after the damage. Also, it is not allowed to calculate the wages (income) received by the victim after causing damage to his health as compensation for damages (Part 2 of Article 1006 of the Criminal Code). For example, if a miner, after receiving an occupational disease, carries out business activities that bring more income than his previous work in his specialty, this situation cannot change the amount of compensation assigned to him in connection with the damage to his health⁹. The amount of compensation can be increased based on the law, individual or collective labor contract, as well as civil law contract.

In order to exercise the right to receive compensation for lost wages (income), it is necessary to determine its composition and size. The victim's lost wages (earnings) include all types of taxable income, both from the main job and from the substitute job. One-time payments (for example, compensation for unused vacation, severance pay) are not taken into account. The lost salary (income) includes income from business activities based on the data of the tax inspectorate, as well as author's fees (Part 2 of Article 1006 of the FC). All types of income are accounted for in amounts calculated before withholding taxes.

The amount of lost wages (income) is determined based on the following: a) average monthly wages (income); b) the period of loss of the opportunity to receive wages (income) in connection with the damage; c) degree of loss of ability to work.

If the victim has never worked before or is able to work, the amount of lost income (at his request) is determined on the basis of his earnings before the dismissal or the usual salary for an employee with his qualifications in a certain field. In any case, the average monthly income calculated in this way cannot be less than the minimum subsistence level of the population of working age, established by law in the country¹⁰.

If, before the damage to health, the victim's work (income) has undergone stable changes, his property situation has improved (for example, he was transferred to a higher-paying job, joined a job after graduation), the law applies only to the salary that the citizen received or should receive after the corresponding changes (income) allows.

⁸ Bogdanov D.E. Nekotorye voprosy vozmeshcheniya vreda, prichinennogo zdorovyu poterpevshego // Rossiyskaya justice. 2012. – No. 3. – S. 2-4.

⁹ Grazhdanskoe pravo: Uchebnik / V.Yu. Borisov, E.S. Getman, O.V. Gutnikov and Dr.; pod ed. O.N. Sadikova. - M.: CONTRACT, INFRA-M, 2007. - T. 2. - 608 p.

¹⁰ Yukovich, Ya. E. Vozmeshchenie vreda, prichinennogo jizni ili zdorovyu grajdanina // Molodoy uchenyy. 2015. – No. 13 (93). - S. 532-537. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/93/20548/> (data obrascheniya: 29.08.2024).